

Synthesis of Some 1, 5-Benzodiazepines: Part I.

S. U. KULKARNI and K. A. THAKAR

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad.

Manuscript received 25 April 1975; accepted 23 June 1975.

Various 2,4-disubstituted 1,5-benzodiazepines were prepared by condensing 1,3-diones with *o*-phenylenediamine. Study of IR spectra of some 2,4-disubstituted 1,5-benzodiazepines revealed that 1,5-benzodiazepines cannot be completely represented by the dianil form. Contribution of imino form is considerable. Seven 1,3-diones and one substituted *o*-hydroxy acetophenone are also being reported for the first time.

THE first compound of 1,5-benzodiazepine series was prepared by Thiele and Steimmig¹ by condensing acetyl acetone (II, R = R' = Me) with *o*-phenylenediamine (I). Since then extensive study of 1,5-benzodiazepines was not done until late fifties. Literature survey reveals that a number of 1,5-benzodiazepines have been found to possess biological and pharmaceutical properties. 2,4-Diphenyl-1,5-benzodiazepine, 7-nitro-2,4-dimethyl-1,5-benzodiazepine, 7-amino-2,4-dimethyl-1,5-benzodiazepine and 7-bis-(2-chloro ethyl)-amino-2,4-dimethyl-1,5-benzodiazepine have been found to possess cancerostatic² activity. In view of this 1,5-benzodiazepines having various substituents at 2- and 4-positions were prepared.

1,3-Diones used in this work have R as substituted phenyl and R' as phenyl. 1,3-Diones listed in Table 1 have been prepared for the first time by the Baker-Venkatraman transformation from the corresponding esters.

2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-5'-ethyl acetophenone was prepared by the Fries migration of 2-chloro-4-ethyl-phenyl acetate. Melting point of this acetophenone was found to be 74° (2,4-DNP 170°).

1,5-Benzodiazepines (III) were prepared by condensing the respective 1,3-diones with *o*-phenylenediamine in alcohol-acetic acid medium. All the compounds thus obtained were crystalline solids. 1,3-Diones in which there is no hydroxyl group in the benzene ring at ortho position w.r.t., the ketonic group gave colourless compounds, whereas 1,3-diones having hydroxyl group in the benzene ring at ortho position

w.r.t., the ketonic group gave yellow coloured crystalline compounds. Alcoholic solutions of these compounds (III) produced violet colouration with hydrochloric acid, a characteristic property of 1,5-benzodiazepines. Violet colouration is believed to be due to the formation of benzodiazepinium ion (V).

V

Melting points, percentage yields and results of elemental analysis of 1,5-benzodiazepines are given in Table 2.

The structure of 1,5-benzodiazepines represented in the dianil form (III) is not certain. Thiele and Steimmig¹ proposed both the structures (III) and (VII) for 1,5-benzodiazepines. Baltrop⁵ *et al.* and Finar⁶ proposed the dianil form only. They have studied the IR spectra of 2,4-dimethyl-1,5-benzo-

VII

diazepine and 2,4-diphenyl-1,5-benzodiazepine in CHCl₃ solution and Nujol mull. Absence of N-H

TABLE 1

IV

R ₁	Compound (IV) R ₂	R ₃	M.P. °C	% Yield	Elemental analysis			
					Found		Required	
					C%	H%	C%	H%
OH	H	H	93	68	75.38	5.42	75.59	5.51
Cl	H	H	141	57	65.48	4.12	65.57	4.01
Br	H	H	137	56	55.99	3.54	56.42	3.45
OH	CH ₃	H	137	67	75.85	5.94	76.12	5.97
H	H	F	139-40	49	69.47	4.38	69.76	4.26
Cl	H	Et	89	54	67.41	5.08	67.43	4.96
Cl	H	Cl	137	49	57.84	3.32	58.25	3.23

stretching band (~3300 cm⁻¹) and presence of C-H stretching bands (~2950 cm⁻¹ and ~2820 cm⁻¹) of methylene group supported dianil form (III).

Lloyd and Marshall⁷ proposed structure (VII) to be preferable to (III). These authors⁸ later stated that a tautomeric shift to structure (VII) takes place during or after protonation. Vaisman^{3,4} considered structure (V) for 1,5-benzodiazepinium ion. Barry⁹ *et al.* stated in the discussion of NMR spectra of some 1,5-benzodiazepines that the contribution from structure (VII) cannot be completely precluded because the spectra were scanned at a low frequency. Low frequency used for scanning and methanol used as a solvent might have obscured some resonance features.

IR spectra of 1,5-benzodiazepines prepared in this work were taken in KBr disc. All spectra showed N-H stretching band near 3300 cm⁻¹ (Table 3). Bands due to methylene group were absent. This leads to conclude that 1,5-benzodiazepines can best be represented as resonating structures (III) ↔ (VII) with larger contribution of the latter.

All the compounds (Table 2) have been sent for activity testing to the SK & F Laboratories, Philadelphia, U.S.A. The reports of activity of these compounds are awaited.

Experimental

A) Preparation of 3'-chloro-5'-ethyl-2'-hydroxy acetophenone :

To a mixture of 2-chloro-4-ethyl phenol (22 g) and pyridine (5 ml) acetic anhydride (25 ml) was added

slowly with stirring. Temperature was not allowed to rise above 20°. After half an hour the reaction mixture was poured on cold water. The organic layer was washed successively with dilute hydrochloric acid, water, dilute sodium hydroxide solution and again with water. The extract was dried over anhydrous CaCl₂. 2-Chloro-4-ethyl-phenyl acetate distilled over at 250°-2°. Yield 25 g

2-Chloro-4-ethyl-phenyl acetate (20 g) and finally powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (16 g) were mixed and heated in an oil bath at 150° for 2 hr. The reaction mass was cooled and decomposed by ice and hydrochloric acid. 3'-Chloro-5'-ethyl-2'-hydroxy acetophenone was isolated by steam distillation and crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles. M.P. 74°. Yield 15 g.

Analysis :

	C%	H%
Found :	60.28	5.59
C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl requires :	60.45	5.54

B) Preparation of β-diketones by hydrolysis of chalcone dibromide :

i) **Preparation of benzal acetophenones (chalcones) :** Acetophenone (60 g, 0.5 mole) and benzaldehyde (52 g, 0.5 mole) were dissolved in ethanol (200 ml). The solution was heated to boiling. To this hot solution 50% sodium hydroxide solution (80 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. Stirring was continued for half an hour. The reaction mixture was cooled in an ice bath, when the precipitate of benzal acetophenone was formed. It was filtered, washed with

TABLE 2

VI

Compound (VI)					M.P. °C	% Yield	Elemental analysis			
R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅			Found		Required	
						C%	H%	C%	H%	
H	H	H	Cl	H	171	51	75.98	4.12	76.24	4.54
H	H	H	Br	H	154	30	70.39	4.18	70.58	4.00
H	H	H	CH ₃	H	166	30	82.39	5.37	82.50	5.31
OH	H	H	H	H	181	52	80.45	4.85	80.76	5.13
OH	CH ₃	H	H	H	151	37	81.36	5.63	80.98	5.52
OH	H	CH ₃	H	H	147	37	80.63	5.45	80.98	5.52
OH	H	H	H	H	188-9	43	80.10	4.80	80.98	5.52
OH	H	CH ₃	Cl	H	215	45	73.29	4.81	73.33	4.71
OH	Cl	H	H	H	155	34	72.60	4.37	72.72	4.33
OH	H	Cl	H	H	183-4	30	72.19	4.14	72.72	4.33
OH	H	H	Cl	H	168	36	72.00	4.54	72.72	4.33
OH	Br	H	H	H	170	27	64.12	3.85	68.45	3.83
OH	H	H	Br	H	197	35	64.36	4.10	64.45	3.83
OH	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	193	28	81.08	5.84	81.17	5.88
OH	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	213	35	80.74	5.93	81.17	5.88
OH	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	168-9	26	81.12	5.85	81.17	5.88
OH	Cl	H	Cl	H	199	20	66.13	3.90	66.14	3.67
OH	H	H	F	H	194	29	76.18	5.65	76.36	5.45
OH	Cl	H	Et	H	203	27	73.74	4.91	73.89	4.92
OH	BENZO	H	H	H	200	28	82.30	5.20	82.87	4.87
OH	H	H	BENZO	H	164	25	82.19	5.02	82.87	4.97

TABLE 3—INFRA RED SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME 1, 5 BENZODIAZEPINES (VI)

Compound VI					ν_{N-H}	ν_{C-N}	δ_{N-H}	C-H Aromatic ring breath- ing	C-H bending vibra- tion of CH ₃ (δ_9)	$\nu_{C-N} <$ δ_{O-H} of phenol	Out of plane bending vibration of C-H aromatics				
R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅							1,2- disubsti- tuted phenyl cm ⁻¹	mono- substituted phenyl cm ⁻¹	3-adj- cent H atoms cm ⁻¹	2-adj- cent H atoms cm ⁻¹	
H	H	H	H	H	3300	1610	1575	1450	—	1325	—	765	745,685	—	—
OH	H	H	H	H	3300	1610	1575	1450	—	1305	1250	760	745,690	—	—
OH	CH ₃	H	H	H	3300	1610	1590	1450	1390	1330	1260	755	745,690	780	—
OH	H	CH ₃	H	H	3300	1610	1580	1450	1385	1325	1255	760	750,690	—	845
OH	H	H	CH ₃	H	3300	1605	1575	1452	1480	1325	1200	775	750,690	—	835
OH	H	H	Cl	H	3300	1625	1575	1450	—	1325	1255	765	750,685	—	825
OH	H	H	Br	H	3280	1610	1565	1450	—	1325	1250	755	745,685	—	820
OH	BENZO	H	H	H	3320	1620	1580	1450	—	1325	1260	755	745,685	—	—

cold water and crystallised from alcohol, M.P. 52°. Yield 58 g (77%).

Similarly prepared were benzal *p*-chloro acetophenone, benzal *p*-bromo acetophenone and benzal *p*-methyl acetophenone.

ii) *Preparation of chalcone dibromides*: Benzalacetophenone (70 g, 0.33 mole) was dissolved in carbon tetrachloride (200 ml.). The solution was cooled in an ice bath and a solution of bromine (54 g, 0.33 mole) was added to the cooled solution, dropwise with stirring. The product obtained was filtered and washed with hot alcohol (80 ml.), m.p. 156°-7°. Yield 100 g (80%).

Similarly prepared were *p*-chloro, *p*-bromo and *p*-methyl-analogues.

iii) *Preparation of β -diketones*: Chalcone dibromide, (92 g, 0.25 mole) and absolute methyl alcohol (80 ml) were placed in a 1 litre flask. A solution of sodium methoxide prepared from sodium, 15 g. and absolute methyl alcohol (150 ml) was added rapidly to the flask and the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (8 ml) was added to neutralise the mixture. To this cold water (100 ml) was added and the flask was cooled. The product obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol. M.P. 73°. Yield 25 g (44.6%).

Remaining three β -diketones were similarly prepared. But they were purified through copper complex. A solution of β -diketone in ethanol and a solution of cupric acetate in ethanol were mixed to form green copper complex. This complex was filtered, dried and digested with 50% hydrochloric acid. The product obtained was crystallised from ethanol.

C) *Preparation of β -diketones by the Baker-Venkatraman Transformation method*

i) *Esterification*: Substituted 2-hydroxy acetophenone (0.05 mole), and dry pyridine (5 ml) were placed in 100 ml flask. Benzoyl chloride (0.06 mole) was added to the flask dropwise with stirring. During the addition temperature was maintained below 20°. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and poured on a mixture of crushed ice and concentrated hydrochloric acid. The product obtained was filtered, washed successively with water, 2% sodium hydroxide solution and again water and crystallised from alcohol or alcohol-water mixture.

In some cases solid product was not separated. In such cases organic layer was extracted with ether, ethereal layer was washed successively with water, 2% sodium hydroxide solution and again water. The extract was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. The solvent was evaporated and the thick syrupy paste obtained was used for the B.V. transformation without further purification.

ii) *The B.V. Transformation*: Substituted 2'-benzoyloxy acetophenone (0.03 mole) was dissolved in pyridine (15 ml). Powdered anhydrous potassium hydroxide was added to it and the reaction mixture was stirred for 20 min when a thick yellow paste was formed. It was poured on a mixture of crushed ice and concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 ml). The compound obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol or alcohol-acetic acid mixture.

D) *Condensation of *o*-phenylene diamine with β -diketones*

A mixture of *o*-phenylene diamine (0.01 mole), β -diketone (0.01 mole), ethanol (15 ml) and glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitate formed was crystallised from alcohol or alcohol-acetic acid mixture.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the authorities of the Marathwada University for awarding a junior research fellowship to one of them (S.U.K.).

References

1. J. THIELE and G. STEIMMIG, *Ber*, 1907, 40, 935.
2. K. V. LEVSHINA, E. I. YUMASHEVA, T. S. ANDRIANOVA, L. P. GLAZYRINA, T. S. SAFONOVA and A. I. KRAVCHENKO (Vses. Nauch. Issled. Khim. Pharm. Inst. Moscow), *Puti Sin. Instancii, Protivoop. Ukholevykh*, 1970, No. 3, 257; *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, 75, 35976.
3. S. B. VAISMAN, *Trans. Inst. Chem. Kharkov. Univ.*, 1938, 4, 157.
4. S. B. VAISMAN, *Chem. Abs.*, 1940, 34, 5847.
5. J. A. BALDROP, C. G. RICHARDS, D. M. RUSSEL and G. RYBACK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1132.
6. I. L. FINAR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4094.
7. D. LLOYD and D. R. MARSHALL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2597.
8. D. LLOYD, E. H. MCDUGALL and D. R. MARSHALL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 3785.
9. W. J. BARRY, I. L. Finar and E. F. MOONEY, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1965, 21, 1095.